

Structural analysis of the oxyluciferin emitting species in aqueous and luciferase media

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System Preparation and Molecular Dynamics simulations

Tleap input example

Listing S1: Example of the tleap input file to perform the setup of the system.

```
source leaprc.gaff2
source leaprc.protein.ff19SB
source leaprc.water.tip3p
source leaprc.custom

loadamberparams phenolate-keto_S0.frmod
loadamberparams AMP.frmod

loadoff phenolate-keto_S0.lib
```

```

loadoff AMP.lib

SYS=loadpdb system.pdb
solvateOct SYS TIP3PBOX 12.0
addIons2 SYS Na+ 0

savepdb SYS final_system.pdb
saveamberparm SYS final_system.prmtop final_system.rst7
quit

```

Molecular dynamics inputs

Consecutively to the preparation of the system, the initial structure was minimized using the input shown in Listing S2.

Listing S2: Example of the input file for the initial minimisation of the structure to perform the classical Molecular Dynamics simulations.

Minimization input file in explicit solvent

```

&cntrl
  ! Minimization options
  imin=1,          ! Turn on minimization
  ntx=1,          ! Read position but not velocities
  irest=0,        ! Do not restart the simulation
  maxcyc=10000,   ! Maximum number of minimization cycles
  nccyc=5000,     ! Method switched from steepest descent
                  ! to conjugate gradient after NCCYC
  ntb=1,          ! PBC cte V
  iwrap=1,

```

```

! Potential energy function options
cut=13.0,          ! Nonbonded cutoff in Angstroms
fswitch=11.0,     ! Van der Waal cutoff

! Restraint options
nmropt=1,        ! Restraints

! Control how often information is printed to the output file
ntpr=100,        ! Print energies every 100 steps
ntwx=0,          ! No trajectory file
/
&wt type = 'END' /

```

Then, the minimized structure was heated by means of the input in Listing S3 considering an initial interval of 500 ps in which the system was gradually heated followed by 500 ps used to stabilize it.

Listing S3: Example of the input file for the heating of the minimised structure.

Heat

```

&cntrl
imin=0,          ! Turn off minimization
ntx=1,           ! Read position but not velocities
irest=0,         ! Do not restart the simulation

nstlim=500000,  ! Perform MD for 500,000 steps
dt=0.002,       ! 2 fs time step
ntf=2, ntc=2,   ! Shake hydrogen atoms

```

```

tempi=0.0,      ! Initial temperature
temp0=300.0,   ! Target temperature

! Control how often information is printed to the output file
ntpr=100,      ! Energy infor will be printed every ntp steps
ntwx=100,      ! Coordinates written to file every ntwx steps

! Potential energy function options
cut=13.0,      ! Nonbonded cutoff in Angstroms
fswitch=11.0,  ! Van der Waal cutoff

! Ensemble control
ntb=1,         ! PBC cte V
ntp=0,         ! No pressure scaling (Default)
ntt=3,         ! Langevin dynamics
gamma_ln=2.0, ! Collision frequency in ps-1

! Wrap coordinates when printing them to the same unit cell
nmropt=1,
iwrap=1,

ig=-1,        ! Random seed to use to generate velocities
/
! Change conditions during simulation
! Simulation increases T from 0 to 300K during steps 0 to 250000
&wt type='TEMP0', istep1=0, istep2=250000, value1=0.0, value2=300.0 /
! Keep T cte for the rest of the simulation

```

```

&wt type='TEMP0', istep1=250001, istep2=500000, value1=300.0,
                                                    value2=300.0 /
&wt type='END' /

```

Finally, as shown in the input in Listing S4, the system was allowed to evolve for 1 μ s.

Listing S4: Example of the input file for the production of the Molecular Dynamics simulation.

A NPT simulation for common production-level simulations

```

&cntrl
    imin=0,                ! No minimization
    irest=1,               ! This IS a restart of an old MD simulation
    ntx=5,                 ! So our inpcrd file has velocities

    ! Temperature control
    ntt=3,                 ! Langevin dynamics
    gamma_ln=1.0,         ! Friction coefficient (ps-1)
    temp0=303.15,         ! Target temperature
    ig=-1,                 ! Seed for velocities

    ! Potential energy control
    cut=13.0,              ! nonbonded cutoff, in Angstroms
    fswitch=11.0,         ! Force-based switching

    ! MD settings
    nstlim=500000000,     ! 1 micros total
    dt=0.002,             ! time step (ps)

```

```

! SHAKE
ntc=2,          ! Constrain bonds containing H
ntf=2,          ! Do not calculate forces of bonds with H

! Control how often information is printed
ntpr=1000,      ! Print energies every 1000 steps
ntwx=25000,     ! Print coords every 25000 steps to the traj
ntwr=10000,     ! Print a restart file every 10K steps
ntxo=2,         ! Write NetCDF format
ioutfm=1,       ! Write NetCDF format (always do this!)

! Wrap coordinates when printing them to the same unit cell
iwrap=1,
nmropt=1,

! Constant pressure control.
barostat=1,     ! Berendsen barostat
ntp=1,          ! 1=isotropic
pres0=1.0,      ! Target external pressure, in bar

! Set water atom/residue names for SETTLE recognition
watnam='WAT',   ! Water residues are named WAT
owtnm='O',      ! Water oxygens are named O
/

&ewald
vdwmeth = 0,

```

Root mean square displacement of the protein

Figure S1: RMSD of the protein for the MD trajectories with the four OLU chromophores in the (A) S_0 and (B) S_1 electronic states.

Root mean square displacement of the OLU chromophores in aqueous media

As it can be observed in Figure S2, even though the chromophores are aligned before the root mean square displacement (RMSD) measurement, they still present large oscillations. In the case of the ground state the phenolate-enolate OLU presents the largest oscillations and the phenol-keto, the lowest while both phenolate-keto and phenol-enolate present similar RMSD values. S_1 aqueous simulations present a different trend in RMSD. In this case, both enolate forms present a similar RMSD value, that is lower than those of S_0 simulations. However, the keto forms present larger oscillations in the excited state, specially the monoanion, for which the large oscillations arise from the population of the three possible minima within

the only torsional degree of freedom that is truly able to rotate, the SCCS dihedral angle (see Figure 1).

Figure S2: Root mean square displacement of each of the OLU chromophores in the (A) S_0 and (B) S_1 electronic states in aqueous media.

Change in the SCCS dihedral of the phenol-keto OLU in the S_0

As it can be observed in Figure S3, at the beginning of the simulation the HB acceptor of SER349 is only close to the N atom of the benzothiazole moiety of the OLU, the O of the benzothiazole moiety is close to SER316 and LYS531 and the O of the thiazole moiety is relatively far to both GLY318 and GLY343. However at around 61 ns of simulation (Figures S4(A,B)), the distances between the N atoms and the O of the thiazole moiety with SER349 (Figure S3(C)) and between the O atom of the benzothiazole moiety and GLY318 and GLY343 (Figure S3(F)) start to decrease and, at the same time, the chromophore moves away from SER316 and LYS531 (Figure S3(G)). This movement, which comprehends

the simulation time between the first 2 vertical lines, takes 7 ns and it is accompanied by the separation of the chromophore away from AMP (Figure S3(H)). After this, the system reorganizes. The N atoms and the O atom of the thiazole moiety of the OLU move away from SER349, remaining close to one another, in contrast to the initial situation (Figure S3(C)). At around 125 ns of simulation, the distance with SER316 starts to increase, while it remains similar for LYS531 induced by the positioning of the HB donor of SER349 at an equidistance position from the N atoms and the O atom of the thiazole moiety of the OLU (Figures S3(C,G)). This conformational change allows an extra water molecule to enter inside the pocket bridging the SER349 and AMP at 170 ns, between the next two vertical lines (Figure S3(B) and Figure S4(C)). Consecutively, two additional water molecules enter the cavity (Figure S4(D)), tilting the chromophore and generating a more polar environment in the side of the SER349, thus giving an extra push for the conformational change of the OLU from the s-trans to the s-cis at 210 ns (Figure S3(A)). Once this happens, one of the water on the side of the SER349 leaves and the chromophore begins to form a HB between the SER349 via the O atom of the thiazole moiety (Figure S3(C) and Figure S4(E)), while the remaining water molecules bridges the HB donor of SER349 with the two N atoms of the OLU. At the same time, the chromophore moves away from GLY318 and GLY343 (Figure S3(F)). When the water molecule that bridged the O of the thiazole moiety with SER349 and AMP leaves (Figure S3(F)), the HB between the OLU and SER349 also disappears (Figure S3(C)) and the phosphate group of the AMP approaches again the chromophore (Figure S3(H)), thus making it impossible to return to the s-trans conformation. Moreover, the benzothiazole moiety moves closer to SER316 although the distance to LYS531 remains similar leading to a different chemical environment than for the s-cis conformation (Figure S3(G)).

Figure S3: (A) SCCS dihedral angle of the phenol-keto OLU during the first 300 ns of the MD simulation in the S_0 . (B-H) Different distances along the simulation. (B) Distances from the O atom of one water molecule to the O atoms of OLU, SER349 and AMP. (C) Distances from the HB donor of SER349 to different HB acceptors of the chromophore. (D,E) Distances from the O atom of two different water molecules to the N atoms of the OLU and the HB acceptors of SER349. (F) Distances from the O atom of of the thiazole moiety to the lateral chain of GLY318 and GLY343. (G) Distances from the O atom of of the benzothiazole moiety to different atoms of SER316 and LYS531 labeled as in the FF. (H) Distances from the C_α of the thiazole moiety of the OLU to the P atom of the AMP. Vertical-dotted lines stress the relevant regions along the simulation and the darkest one represents the conformational change. Horizontal-dotted lines represent the threshold of HB of 3 Å. Taking into account that for some distances there is a H-O bond in between the O-O distance, this line is shifted to 3.98 Å when required.

(A) 61 ns

(B) 68 ns

(C) 180 ns

(D) 202.5 ns

(E) 215 ns

(F) 220 ns

Figure S4: Representative snapshots of the phenol-keto OLU MD simulation in the S_0 during the first 300 ns.